

VORONOI DIAGRAM AS A TOOL FOR ANALYSING DEVELOPMENT IN RAILWAY AND AIR TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE: A EUROPEAN PERSPECTIVE

MARTIN FALE¹, TEA VIZINGER², BOJAN RUPNIK³, TOMAŽ KRAMBERGER⁴

¹ University of Maribor, Faculty of Logistics, Celje, Slovenia, martin.fale1@um.si 0009-0001-6014-1775

² University of Maribor, Faculty of Logistics, Celje, Slovenia, tea.vizinger@um.si 0000-0003-1539-9600

³ University of Maribor, Faculty of Logistics, Celje, Slovenia, bojan.rupnik@um.si 0000-0001-9983-1178

⁴ University of Maribor, Faculty of Logistics, Celje, Slovenia, tomaz.kramberger@um.si 0000-0001-7656-5444

Abstract: *This research examines the use of Voronoi diagram as an effective tool for analyzing the spatial dispersion and accessibility of mobility hubs in Europe, with a particular focus on railway and air infrastructure. Using ArcGIS Pro tool, we generated Voronoi sets representing selected railway stations and airports within the study area. Based on the size of the Voronoi sets, we assessed the development and coverage of each mode of transport and identified areas with less developed railway infrastructure. Such areas are in Northern, Eastern, and Southeastern Europe. Central Europe, Italy, and the Iberian Peninsula are areas where railway infrastructure is comparable to air infrastructure. The average Voronoi set for railway stations is larger due to their lower number, while airports have smaller average Voronoi set because they are more numerous and distributed more densely. The results show that Voronoi diagram provide clear visualization of accessibility to mobility hubs and are useful for spatial planning and as a decision support tool.*

Keywords: *Voronoi diagram, rail transportation, air transportation, Geographic Information System.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The tendency to use rail transportation as an alternative to air travel for distances up to 1000 km in the European Union (EU) is increasing. Currently, the environmental aspect is at the forefront, as (high-speed) rail is significantly less harmful to the environment than air travel (European Environmental Agency, 2021). Promoting the use of (high-speed) rail as a competitor to air travel faces the challenge of inadequate or non-existent infrastructure for high-speed trains. To fully benefit from rail transportation at the EU level, adequate rail infrastructure must be ensured. Everyone must have access to a railway station where a train stops that can take them to their destination in a travel time comparable to that of an airplane. If an individual does not have a railway station near their point of departure but does have access to an airport, the airport becomes the accessibility hub for continuing their journey toward their destination. Decision-makers must therefore identify areas where investments in specific types of transport infrastructure are necessary to provide an alternative to the current dominant mode of transport. This can be done using a Voronoi diagram.

Burkey et al. (2011) define Voronoi diagram as a simple geometric construct with a wide range of applications. A Voronoi diagram consists of Voronoi sets. Each set represents a region associated with a specific central point, and this region contains all points that are closer to the central point than to any other central point in the given space. Introducing weights to the central points leads to weighted central points, which in turn attract a larger set of points than they would otherwise. Dong (2008) notes that Voronoi sets in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are typically based on unweighted central points. They divide the plane into distinct regions, a collection of planar sections. Marianov and Eiselt (2024), in their review of the history of location models, highlight the importance of Voronoi diagram in location theory. This is further supported by Boonprong et al. (2024), who describe the Voronoi diagram as a powerful tool for spatial analysis and decision support. In our research, we aim to explore whether Voronoi diagram can help identify areas where rail transport is at a disadvantage compared to air transport or vice versa.

2. RELATED WORK

Kloskowski et al. (2024) highlighted the relevance of using Voronoi diagrams as a tool for planning the spatial development of urban areas. Their study focused on determining optimal locations for shopping centers,

based on the Movement of People indicator. The Voronoi sets were generated for a selected area in Poland, covering the cities of Gdansk and Gdynia. Each Voronoi set represented the value of this indicator: smaller areas indicated higher levels of physical activity among the population, while larger areas signified lower levels of physical activity in a given region. Raghu Kisore and Koteswaraiah (2017) addressed the problem of ATM placement. They used Voronoi sets to determine the optimal number and distribution of ATMs. The sets represented potential locations, while waiting times at each ATM, affected by population density and the types of commercial activities in the area, were used as weights. Thus, the Voronoi set represented the influence zones of each ATM. The study did not specify the basis used for generating the Voronoi diagram.

Figuerska et al. (2022) used Voronoi diagram to assess accessibility to selected facilities for the elderly in the city of Olsztyn, Poland. They divided the area into uniformly sized cells, Voronoi sets, and calculated the number of such facilities within each cell, focusing on those with high social significance for seniors. Jiao and Feng (2024) explored the problem of shelter location as a part of emergency planning. Their study included the use of weighted Voronoi diagram. Based on published figures, it appears they divided the selected area, Lindian County in Heilongjiang Province, into uniformly sized cells. They combined Voronoi sets with OD Cost Matrix analysis results to represent the coverage area of each shelter, considering the number of residences and a digital elevation model in the context of flood risk. Shahparvari et al. (2020) examined the distribution of fire stations in Melbourne. Based on their results, they proposed locations to establish new fire station or to relocate existing ones to achieve better coverage. Voronoi diagram was used as a tool to define the boundaries of areas that are closer to a particular fire station than to any other.

Several studies using Voronoi diagram tool have focused on the problem of locating electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. Prakobkaew and Sirisumrannukul (2022) divided selected provinces in Thailand into uniformly sized cells, to represent the number of electric vehicles in each area. They used Voronoi sets to illustrate the service areas of public EV charging stations. Jordan et al. (2022) investigated the problem of EV charging infrastructure in Valencia, Spain. They used Voronoi diagram to show how the coverage area of individual charging stations decreases as the number of stations increases. The coverage area of each charging station was defined as the intersection of a circle representing the station's influence zone and the Voronoi set. Boonprong et al. (2024) emphasized the advantage of using Voronoi diagram for spatial analysis. By analyzing coverage areas, they assessed the current distribution of EV charging stations and proposed locations for new ones. The Voronoi sets were generated using ArcGIS tool and were based on population density, proximity to roads of different categories, and land use patterns. The underlying data for generating the Voronoi sets were population data.

Mota et al. (2014) focused on determining the locations of suburban railway stations in the city of Brasília using weighted Voronoi sets, generated with ArcGIS tool. Each Voronoi set represented the relationship between a potential railway station site and the demand for rail transport. Based on their findings, the authors proposed a framework for establishing a railway corridor in the selected area.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study is part of a broader research project. The main idea is to create a model that determines, for any location within a given area, which mode of transport, airplane, train or another, is optimal within a predefined radius based on various factors such as time, cost and sustainability. Familiarity with the research context facilitated the development of the methodological framework of this research. First, we defined the concept of the Voronoi diagram and its unit, the Voronoi set. A literature review was conducted using Science Direct and Web of Science databases. Initially, we searched using the keywords Voronoi AND mobility hubs AND accessibility, but no results were found in either database. This indicate the novelty of research that uses Voronoi diagram to assess accessibility to mobility hubs. We then expanded our search with keywords Voronoi AND transportation, Voronoi AND hubs, and Voronoi AND GIS. Accordingly, we included the findings of nine studies in our review of the related work. The review of related work clearly indicates the importance of the Voronoi diagram in location theory.

The study area includes EU countries, the United Kingdom, Norway, and Switzerland. Within the study area, airports with more than 30 connections were considered, focusing on flight connections up to 1000 km in length. Railway stations were selected based on data from the Omio portal, considering additional information from the Eurail Association about railway stations currently designated as part of the existing high-speed rail network in Europe (Eurail, 2025; Flight Connections, 2025; Omio, 2025). The initial list of 299 airports and 171 railway stations was compiled in August 2023, and its accuracy was verified in May 2025.

For the spatial analysis, we used the software tool ArcGIS Pro, version 3.5.0. Locations of airports and railway stations were added using the Locate tool, creating point layers for airports and railway stations. Both

layers were created in the Geographic Coordinate System WGS 1984. The polygon layer of Europe from Geofabrik served as the base for selecting the study area (Geofabrik, 2025). To determine the influence zones of airports and railway stations, we created Voronoi sets using the Create Thiessen Polygons tool, one for airports and one for railway stations. To ensure that Voronoi sets were generated for the entire study area, we set the Processing Extent in Environments to Extent of a layer, selecting the polygon layer of the study area. For better readability of the Shape Area units of the Voronoi sets, we reprojected the generated Voronoi polygon layers into the projected coordinate system ETRS 1989 using the Project tool. This allowed us to obtain area data for each Voronoi set in metric units, meters. Several assumptions were also taken into consideration. The measure used to assess the development of a particular mode of transport is the area of the Voronoi sets, which represents the region served by an individual airport or railway station. The choice of the Omio platform is based on the following assumption: An individual's journeys between various locations gradually contribute to the recognition of major transport flows. This, in turn, leads to the establishment of regular connections using different modes of transport, which aim to meet the demand for travel along these routes. Omio, a platform designed to facilitate travel between frequently visited points, offers these locations for selection. Additionally, Omio can suggest alternative modes of transport, including air, rail, or road travel, which is useful for our research.

The presented example is based on the following algorithm: In Step 1, we define the analysis area as a bounded subset of the pane (by loading a polygon layer representing the selected area into ArcGIS Pro). In Step 2, we define the set of all generators or seeds (point layers representing airports and railway stations located within the analysis area). In Step 3, we generate Voronoi sets around these generators or seeds within the bounded subset of the pane (using the Create Thiessen Polygons tool in ArcGIS Pro).

The shape of the Voronoi sets is influenced by the bounded subset of the pane, the number of generators or seeds, airports and railway stations, and the software environment in which they are generated. Since this study was conducted using ArcGIS Pro, the final form of the Voronoi sets is determined by the specific method implemented in the software. In ArcGIS Pro, Voronoi sets are created by first connecting the input points into a triangulated irregular network that satisfies the Delaunay criterion. The perpendicular bisectors of the triangle edges are then calculated, defining the edges of the sets. Additionally, the final boundary of the output layer is slightly larger than the extent of the input points (ESRI, 2025).

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Results

In the study, we included 299 airports and 171 railway stations. On average, the Voronoi set area for an airport is 16,258.44 km², while for a railway station, it is 28,428.46 km². The smallest Voronoi set area for an airport is 1,267.27 km², covered by Ålesund Airport. The largest Voronoi set area for an airport is 68,285.55 km², covered by Tromsø Airport. The smallest Voronoi set area for a railway station is 1,052.51 km², covered by München railway station. The largest Voronoi set area for a railway station is 469,818.37 km², covered by Sundsvall railway station. The average area of a Voronoi set for railway stations is larger because there are fewer stations compared to airports. The average area of a Voronoi set for airports is smaller because there are more airports, resulting in a more uniformly distributed division of areas. The Voronoi diagram for air transportation is shown in Figure 1, while the Voronoi diagram for rail transportation is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Voronoi diagram for air transportation

Figure 2: Voronoi diagram for rail transportation

4.2 Discussion

By comparing Figure 1 and Figure 2, we can identify areas where a lack of railway infrastructure is evident, as indicated by the larger area covered by individual Voronoi set. In Northern, Eastern, and Southeastern Europe, there is a noticeable underdevelopment of railway infrastructure. While the geographic and climatic conditions in Northern Europe act as limiting factors, Eastern and Southeastern Europe does not face such extreme conditions, suggesting that the underdevelopment of railway infrastructure in this region is primarily due to other factors. The dominant mode of transport in Northern, Eastern, and Southeastern Europe is therefore air travel, as indicated by the number of airports in these areas. In contrast, Central Europe, Italy, and the Iberian Peninsula have a much denser distribution of railway stations compared to other parts of the area covered in our research. It is relevant to highlight the case of the United Kingdom and its railway stations. The reason why only one railway station from the United Kingdom is included in the analysis is that this station serves as the starting or ending point for rail connections between the British Isles and mainland Europe. As a result, the Voronoi set representing the area around this station covers a significantly larger area than the average.

From the comparison between airport and railway station areas, Voronoi sets, we can observe that airport areas are much more uniform than those of railway stations. This is also reflected in the statistical data, with the standard deviation for airport areas being 11,566.92 km², while for railway stations it is 61,320.46 km². This can be also linked to the following fact: airport complexes occupy a much larger spatial area compared to railway stations, but they can more easily overcome geographical constraints such as bodies of water, hilly terrain, or highly urbanized areas, which on the other hand limit the construction of railway tracks. This enables a more uniform distribution of airports across the territory, as they can be more easily integrated into the spatial layout.

5. CONCLUSION

The primary value of this research lies in the visual insights provided by the graphical material, which can be useful for both decision-makers and the public. The size of Voronoi set area can be used to assess the state of infrastructure in a given region. Smaller polygon areas indicate a higher number of seeds, airports or railway stations, while larger polygon areas suggest a lower number of such facilities. This allows us to identify regions with well-developed or underdeveloped infrastructure. Furthermore, this approach can support modeling of transportation mode choice, particularly in the context of selecting between air travel and high-speed rail, a topic of increasing relevance within the EU. Based on the findings, we argue that the Voronoi diagram is an effective tool that can be applied within the framework of location theory.

One limitation of this study is that we focused exclusively on airports recognized as major mobility hubs for interregional and international travel, leaving out smaller airports that also serve passengers and play an important role in connecting certain areas. Similarly, for railway stations, we included only those recognized as mobility hubs for travel between frequently visited locations, omitting a significant number of other (smaller) stations. A potential extension of the research would involve incorporating an additional criterion, population distribution, which can reflect the demand for transport, into the analysis by using weighted Voronoi sets. We could exclude islands, such as Sardinia, from the covered area. This could be justified by the fact that, when comparing air and rail travel, we should analyze them based on comparable journeys. The ability of airplanes to cross bodies of water more easily gives them an advantage over trains. However, individuals living on islands can still use trains for their travels on the mainland of Europe once they have crossed the body of water separating the island from the mainland. Also, the results could be presented by individual countries/regions. This would allow for the development of measures at the national/regional level, as there are significant differences between countries/regions. Measures aimed at promoting the use of (high-speed) rail would certainly differ for Spain and Italy compared to Poland, Romania, or Bulgaria, as the current development of high-speed rail infrastructure gives the former a clear advantage.

We would also like to highlight a general methodological issue observed in other studies. Many studies do not specify the basis for generating the Voronoi diagram layers. These layers may be created from random points to represent the influence area of a certain feature, or as a uniform grid where each cell has the same area and serves as a baseline for calculating specific indicators. While experts in the field may understand the basis of the Voronoi diagram from context, this may not be clear to other readers, which can reduce the clarity and transparency of the research results. As an example, in the studies by Raghu Kisore and Koteswaraiah (2017) and Jordan et al. (2022), it was not specified on what basis the Voronoi sets were generated, and based on the research results, we were also unable to determine the procedure.

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